

Development and Utilization of Nanotechnology in Medicine and the Built Environment.

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Abstract

This paper critically examines the historical evolution and practical applications of both nanoscience and nanotechnology, tracing their origins from ancient times to the contemporary era. Nanoscience, which scrutinizes structures and molecules within the nanometre scale, serves as the precursor to nanotechnology, a revolutionary innovation that has gained prominence in the 21st century. The groundwork laid by visionaries such as Richard Feynman and Norio Taniguchi has been pivotal in conceptualizing nanotechnology, envisioning the manipulation of matter at the molecular level. The synthesis approaches employed in nanotechnology, categorized as top-down and bottom-up, present a spectrum of methods for the creation of nanostructures. This diversity underscores the complexity and adaptability of techniques in this field. Examining the historical timeline, spanning over 4,500 years, sheds light on humanity's early engagement with nanostructures, portraying a trajectory that has culminated in modern nanotechnology. Significant milestones in this scientific journey, from Faraday's colloidal gold to contemporary advancements, highlight the continuous refinement of nanotechnological methodologies. Nanoparticles, particularly in the realm of drug delivery, have emerged as invaluable tools, showcasing capabilities in controlled release and targeted delivery, notably in the burgeoning field of nano-oncology. The influence of nanotechnology extends beyond the biomedical sphere to the built environment, exerting a profound impact on construction, materials, energy efficiency, and sustainability. Innovations such as nano-enabled coatings, lightweight materials, and the recycling of nanomaterials illustrate the transformative potential of nanotechnology in reshaping various aspects of the built environment.

Keywords: *Nanotechnology, Nanomaterials, sustainability*

i) Introduction

Nanotechnology is a unique multidisciplinary idea of the 21st century that involves the study of matter at the nanoscale range. It has connected gaps in natural sciences, materials science, engineering, and medicine, with implausible relevance in diverse sectors (Elegbede and Lateef , 2019). Nanotechnology is concerned with the re-engineering or fabrication of materials and devices by controlling and manipulating the matter at the atomic level. At the nanoscale, properties of materials are changed from that of the larger scales which represent the “nano-effects” that eventually determine the nature and characteristics that we are familiar with at the “macro-scale” and this is where the influence of nanotechnology comes in; if elements are manipulated at the nanoscale, this can affect their macro-properties and create significantly new materials and processes (Rawat, Kumar and Verma, 2015). Various applications in nanoscience and nanotechnology have continue to increase the possibility of synthesis of nano-sized materials (1-100 nm) in various areas of human activities, thereby bridging the gap across the various frontiers of knowledge. This field of

technology has attracted and keeps attracting great interests owing to its extensive applications in diverse phases of life endeavours. In broad-spectrum, nanotechnology deals basically with the production and stabilization of nanomaterials and nanoparticles of different types (Elegbede et al., 2018).

Nanotechnology stands out as a groundbreaking innovation of the 21st century, enabling the transformation of nanoscience theories into practical applications across the nanometer scale. In the United States, the National Nanotechnology Initiative (NNI) defines nanotechnology as a field encompassing nanoscale science, engineering, and technology (1 to 100 nm), leading to novel applications in various domains like chemistry, physics, biology, medicine, engineering, and electronics. It is vital to differentiate between nanoscience and nanotechnology. Nanoscience integrates physics, materials science, and biology, focusing on the manipulation of materials at the atomic and molecular scales. In contrast, nanotechnology involves the ability to observe, measure, manipulate, assemble, monitor, and manufacture matter on a nanometre scale. While historical reports on nanoscience and technology exist, there is a lack of comprehensive studies summarizing the revolutionary events in this field. Therefore, it is essential to compile key events in nanoscience and technology to gain a thorough understanding of their progression over time.

ii) **The Visionaries Behind Nanotechnology**

The concept of nanotechnology was introduced by Richard Feynman, an acclaimed American physicist and Nobel Prize laureate, in 1959. During the annual meeting of the American Physical Society at the California Institute of Technology (Caltech), Feynman delivered a lecture titled "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom." In this influential lecture, he pondered, "Why can't we write the entire 24 volumes of the Encyclopedia Britannica on the head of a pin?" Feynman envisioned the use of machines to construct smaller machines, reaching down to the molecular level. The realization of Feynman's theories over time has established him as the pioneer and father of modern nanotechnology.

In 1974, Norio Taniguchi, a Japanese scientist, played a pivotal role by being the first to coin and define the term "nanotechnology" after a fifteen-year gap. Taniguchi's definition emphasized that nanotechnology primarily involves the manipulation, consolidation, and deformation of materials at the level of individual atoms or molecules (Guttula, Kishore and Lakshmi, 2020). These creative minds, Feynman and Taniguchi, have left an indelible mark on the inception and development of nanotechnology.

Following Richard Feynman's groundbreaking foray into the realm of nanotechnology, researchers have since explored two distinct methods to unlock the diverse possibilities of nanostructure synthesis, captivating the attention of numerous scientists. These production methods can be broadly categorized into two approaches: top-down and bottom-up, each distinguished by differences in consistency, speed, and cost.

A. Top-Down Approach: The top-down approach involves the reduction of bulk material into nanosized structures or particles. Drawing inspiration from methods utilized for generating micron-sized particles, top-down synthesis methods are generally simpler. These methods rely on the removal or division of bulk material, or they leverage the miniaturization of bulk manufacturing processes to achieve the desired structure with suitable properties. Despite

its simplicity, the top-down approach faces challenges related to surface structure imperfections. Techniques within this approach include high-energy wet ball millings, electron beam lithography, atomic force manipulation, gas-phase condensation, aerosol spray, among others. For instance, nanowires produced through lithography in the top-down approach may exhibit surface irregularities, impurities, and structural defects, underscoring the need for precision in this method.

B. Bottom-Up Technique: In contrast, the 'bottom-up' approach serves as an alternative method, offering the potential to generate less waste and be more cost-effective. This technique involves constructing a material from the bottom, atom-by-atom, molecule-by-molecule, or cluster-by-cluster. While some bottom-up methods are still in the developmental stage, others are making strides and finding commercial applications in nanopowder manufacturing. Notable bottom-up techniques include the organo-metallic chemical route, reverse-micelle route, sol-gel synthesis, colloidal precipitation, hydrothermal synthesis, template-assisted sol-gel, electro-deposition, among others. The bottom-up approach holds promise for creating nanostructures with fewer imperfections and greater precision, making it an attractive option for various applications.

iii) Evolution of Nanomaterial Applications

Ceramic matrix reinforcement has been manipulated by humans for more than 4,500 years, marking an early exploration into the world of nanostructures. Around 4,000 years ago, the Ancient Egyptians engaged in nanomaterial (NM) synthesis through a synthetic chemical process, creating PbS nanoparticles (NPs) with a diameter of approximately 5 nm for hair dye. The Egyptians also pioneered the use of nanometer-sized glass and quartz in the 3rd century BC to produce "Egyptian blue," a synthetic pigment widely employed for decorative purposes in ancient regions of the Roman Empire, including Egypt, Mesopotamia, and Greece.

Metallic NP synthesis through chemical methods dates back to the 14th and 13th centuries BC, where Egyptians and Mesopotamians utilized metals in glass manufacturing, marking the early stages of the metallic nanoparticle era (Schaming, Remita, and Chem, 2015). Instances of synthetic NMs in practical applications include red glass coloured by Cu NPs during the late Bronze Age (1200-1000 BC) and Celtic red enamels containing Cu NPs and cuprous oxide (Cu_2O) from the 400-100 BC period. Notably, the Roman Lycurgus Cups from the 4th century showcased the use of Ag-Au alloy NPs. In the medieval era, stained glass in churches incorporated colloidal Au and Ag NPs to achieve red and yellow hues. During the 9th century, Mesopotamians introduced glazed ceramics for metallic lustre decorations, featuring Ag and/or Cu NPs within the glaze layers, exhibiting iridescent green and blue colors. A similar technique was employed in the mid-19th century for the production of Satsuma glass in Japan, where Cu NPs enhanced the ruby colour. Even in ancient times, clay minerals with nanometer-scale thickness found applications, such as wool and clothes bleaching in Cyprus around 5000 BC.

The scientific exploration of NMs began with Michael Faraday's report on colloidal Au NP synthesis in 1857, providing early insights into NP preparation and optical differences from bulk counterparts. In the 1940s, SiO_2 NPs were manufactured as rubber reinforcement replacements for carbon black. The modern era of nanotechnology saw significant

developments from the early ideas of Feynman to the creation of the Scanning Tunneling Microscope (STM) by Gerd Binnig and Heinrich Rohrer in 1981. This groundbreaking invention led to the development of atomic force microscopes (AFM) and scanning probe microscopes (SPM). In 1985, Robert Curl, Harold Kroto, and Richard Smalley discovered fullerenes or buckyballs, and in 1991, Iijima observed carbon nanotubes (Iijima et al., 1991).

In 2003, Samsung introduced antibacterial technology using ionic Ag NPs in household appliances. Nanoparticles and nanoscale materials found applications in various industries, including auto manufacturing, where they enhanced road adhesion and improved rigidity. Mercedes-Benz introduced NP-based clear coat finishes in 2003, increasing scratch resistance and shine. Additionally, ferrofluids, containing small magnetic NPs, were developed for use in adaptive optics and magnetic mirror telescopes. The accidental discovery of carbon dots (C-dots) by Xu et al. in 2004 opened new possibilities for nanocarbon materials. Graphene, discovered in 2004, became the foundation for various scientific and engineering fields. In 2004, Samsung launched Silver NanoTM, incorporating ionic Ag NPs in household appliances. NPs and nanoscale materials continued to find applications in solar cells, catalysis, and various other fields.

The medical use of nanoparticles gained prominence in drug delivery, with biodegradable polymers offering a less harmful solution. In 1975, Ringdorf proposed a polymer-drug conjugate model for anticancer drug delivery. Passive and active delivery methods have been explored for targeting specific tissues. Nanoparticles have become integral in bioimaging, with advancements in optical imaging, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasound imaging, positron emission tomography (PET), and more. Luminescent and magnetic nanoparticles have been extensively used for bioimaging, and dual-mode nanoparticles capable of simultaneous optical imaging and MRI have been developed. The continuous evolution of nanotechnology promises further innovations and applications in various fields.

iv) Utilizing Nanoparticles as Drug Delivery Systems (DDS)

Drug Delivery Systems (DDS) play a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of various drugs by addressing challenges such as solubility, in vivo stability, pharmacokinetics, and biodistribution. Nanoparticles, with their advantageous characteristics, emerge as promising candidates for DDS. For instance, mixed monolayer-covered gold clusters were employed to deliver a hydrophobic fluorophore (BODIPY) in vitro. BODIPY, known for its infrared absorption and stability, served as a model for cellular delivery. The cationic surface of nanoparticles facilitated the penetration of cell membranes, triggering intracellular glutathione (GSH) activation upon payload release. Notably, the intracellular GSH concentration was approximately 1,000 times higher than the extracellular environment. Fluorogenesis indicated the dye release from the quenching nanoparticle. In mouse embryonic fibroblast cells, the release of a hydrophobic drug analogue was observed, showcasing the potential of nanoparticles in controlled drug delivery.

Researchers have also explored stimuli-responsive nanoparticles, such as mesoporous silica nanoparticles, where thiols like dihydrolipoic acid (DHLA) and dithiothreitol (DTT) triggered the dissolution of porous caps, releasing trapped molecules. This method demonstrated promise in cancer cells, emphasizing the potential for targeted drug delivery in nano-

oncology. Advancements in nano-oncology involve enhancing the efficacy of conventional chemotherapy drugs for various aggressive human cancers. Nanoparticles, antibodies, and cytotoxic agents have been employed to target functional molecules at tumour sites, influencing critical biological processes. Nano-oncology not only reduces systemic toxicity associated with chemotherapy but also enhances tumour response rates.

v) Nanotechnology and the built Environment

Nanotechnology, involving the manipulation of materials at the nanoscale, emerges as a powerful force in the built environment, exerting influence across construction, materials, energy efficiency, and sustainability. In the realm of advanced construction materials, nanoparticles like carbon nanotubes and graphene play a pivotal role in bolstering the mechanical properties of traditional materials such as concrete and steel, resulting in structures that are not only stronger but also more durable. Additionally, the integration of nanoparticles into construction materials enables the creation of self-healing properties, allowing for autonomous repair of cracks and damages over time.

Addressing energy efficiency, nanotechnology introduces nanocoatings that can be applied to building surfaces. These coatings, featuring nanoparticles with thermal insulating properties, enhance insulation, thereby reducing heat transfer through walls and windows. Furthermore, the development of energy-generating materials at the nanoscale opens avenues for sustainable and self-sufficient building systems, harnessing energy from sources like sunlight or vibrations. In the realm of smart and responsive structures, nanoscale sensors integrated into building materials facilitate real-time monitoring of structural health, damage detection, and measurement of environmental conditions. Responsive nanomaterials at the nanoscale demonstrate adaptability, adjusting properties such as transparency, conductivity, or insulation, thereby enhancing a building's functionality and energy efficiency.

Nanotechnology extends its impact to water purification and environmental remediation. Nanoparticles find application in advanced filtration systems for water purification, effectively removing pollutants and contaminants from water sources within construction projects and buildings. Moreover, in the pursuit of air purification, nanotechnology contributes to the development of materials that capture and neutralize indoor pollutants and allergens. Nano-enabled coatings play a role in safeguarding building materials. Anti-corrosion nanocoatings protect against corrosion, extending the lifespan of structures and reducing maintenance costs. Additionally, nano-coatings with hydrophobic or photocatalytic properties create self-cleaning surfaces, minimizing the need for manual cleaning and maintenance.

In the domain of lightweight and high-strength materials, nanotechnology contributes to the development of nanocomposites. These materials, known for their lightweight and robust qualities, find diverse applications in construction, including the production of resilient building components. Lastly, nanotechnology intersects with waste reduction through nanomaterial recycling. By playing a role in the recycling of construction materials, nanotechnology contributes to sustainable building practices and the reduction of waste in the built environment. The multifaceted applications of nanotechnology in the built

environment underscore its transformative potential in reshaping various facets of construction and sustainability.

vi) Conclusion

The evolution of nanomaterials from ancient applications to contemporary innovations is marked by substantial advancements. The visionary contributions of pioneers such as Richard Feynman and Norio Taniguchi have been instrumental in shaping the exploration of synthesis approaches, unraveling the intricacies inherent in both top-down and bottom-up methodologies. The application of nanoparticles in drug delivery, particularly in the realm of nano-oncology, stands as a testament to the transformative potential of nanotechnology in healthcare. The controlled release and targeted delivery facilitated by nanoparticles offer promising avenues for enhancing the effectiveness of medical treatments, with continued research and development poised to revolutionize therapeutic interventions, providing more precise and effective solutions for a variety of medical conditions.

Furthermore, the integration of nanotechnology into the built environment signifies a paradigm shift in construction practices, materials engineering, and sustainable initiatives. Nano-enabled coatings, which augment surface properties, lightweight materials, and innovative waste reduction methods contribute to the versatility and promise of nanotechnology. The built environment stands to gain significantly from these advancements, experiencing improved durability, enhanced energy efficiency, and a reduced environmental footprint. Recommendations for the future centre around fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange among scientists, engineers, and policymakers. This collaborative effort can propel the development of standardized protocols and regulations, ensuring the safe and ethical application of nanotechnology across diverse industries. Additionally, increased investment in research and development will drive the exploration of novel applications, securing nanotechnology's ongoing contribution to sustainable development and its capacity to address emerging challenges.

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